

Enabling Efficient Portrait Segmentation on Embedded Devices

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Abstract—Portrait segmentation (isolating a picture’s subject from the background) has become a key step for applications such as video conferencing, augmented reality, and mobile imaging. Deploying these capabilities directly on low-power devices, including smartphones, action cameras, and even within image sensors themselves, eliminates reliance on external processors, reducing system complexity and power consumption. In this work, we present SINergy, a scalable and hardware-aware portrait segmentation network specifically designed for embedded deployment. SINergy builds upon efficient backbones such as XiNet and PhiNet, optimizing arithmetic intensity, memory access patterns, and operator compatibility rather than conventional FLOP-centric metrics. We systematically evaluate SINergy across heterogeneous platforms, ranging from consumer microcontrollers to small accelerators, single-board computers, and GPU-equipped edge devices. Our experimental results show that SINergy achieves 2× to 5× speedup over existing architectures while preserving accuracy, and delivers the first real-time implementation of portrait segmentation on microcontrollers. Beyond tiny devices, the same hardware-aware principles yield over 80% latency reduction on GPU-equipped platforms. On a Greenwaves GAP9 microcontroller, SINergy requires just 6.4 ms for segmentation under 60 mW of power. These results establish SINergy as a scalable and energy-efficient solution, enabling practical deployment of portrait segmentation across the full spectrum of embedded computing. Code is available at <https://github.com/RickyBenevelli/SINergy>

Index Terms—portrait segmentation, scalable neural networks, tinyML, embedded platforms, efficient architectures

I. INTRODUCTION

Real-time portrait segmentation has become essential for human-centered applications across mobile and embedded devices. From video conferencing background replacement [1] to augmented reality in wearables [2] and mobile portrait enhancement [3], [4], the demand for efficient human figure isolation continues to grow. Bringing these approaches to smaller, low-power devices can enable analysis in platforms such as smartphones, action cameras, and also allow these solutions to be embedded directly within video sensors and small DSP chips. This removes the need for an extra processor

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Fig. 1. Energy efficiency and accuracy–latency trade-offs on Jetson Xavier. Left: frames per Joule (higher is better). Right: EG1800 mIoU versus inference latency (ms; lower is better); bubble size is proportional to energy per inference. SINergy variants achieve markedly higher efficiency while preserving competitive accuracy.

for video analysis and leading to even more significant reductions in system complexity and power demands. However, the transition from cloud-based processing to edge deployment introduces severe constraints in computational resources, memory capacity, and energy consumption that conventional approaches fail to adequately address.

Current lightweight segmentation methods exhibit fundamental limitations for embedded deployment. While parameter-efficient approaches like SINet [5] and ExtremeC3Net [6] achieve reduced model complexity, they employ architectural components poorly suited for embedded hardware, such as depthwise separable convolutions with sub-par arithmetic intensity. Similarly, recent re-parameterization techniques like RCRNet [7] improve training efficiency but overlook platform-specific requirements including memory access patterns and operator support constraints. These limitations become critical in ultra-constrained environments where integer-only arithmetic, restricted operator availability, and stringent memory budgets are characteristic of microcontroller platforms. This gap between accuracy and practical embedded efficiency is highlighted in Figure 1.

Building on recent advances in scalable, hardware-aware

backbones such as the XiNet [8] family, we introduce SINergy, an efficient portrait segmentation network for tiny devices with high compatibility and straightforward scalability across heterogeneous platforms, as shown in Figure 1. Unlike conventional FLOP-centric approaches, SINergy emphasizes real-world efficiency by optimizing arithmetic intensity, memory access patterns, and operator compatibility for embedded hardware. The main contributions of this work are:

- **SINergy**, the first portrait segmentation method capable of running on **microcontroller-scale hardware**.
- A hardware-conscious design: SINergy combines a lightweight decoder with a hardware-aware image encoder to efficiently **scale with the computational and memory resources of the target platform**.
- Extensive evaluation of SINergy across multiple platforms, from ultra-constrained microcontrollers to edge GPUs, demonstrating major improvements in **energy efficiency and inference speed** while maintaining competitive segmentation accuracy.
- An architecture and energy trade-off analysis, which highlights the benefits of **platform-aware network design** for ultra-constrained embedded deployments.

II. RELATED WORK

Portrait segmentation. Early portrait segmentation research builds upon semantic segmentation advances, notably Fully Convolutional Networks (FCNs) [9], encoder-decoder models such as SegNet [10] and U-Net [11], and DeepLab variants [12] with dilated convolutions and Atrous Spatial Pyramid Pooling. However, these models incur high computational cost, making them impractical for embedded deployment. Portrait-specific models such as PortraitFCN+ [13] and boundary-aware designs like BSN [14] improved segmentation quality, while lightweight architectures like PortraitNet [15] adopted MobileNetV2 [16] backbones with depthwise separable convolutions to reduce latency. Nonetheless, efficiency remains insufficient for ultra-low-resource platforms. To bridge this gap, ultra-compact architectures have emerged. SINet [5] proposed a Spatial Squeeze Module and confidence-guided decoding, enabling high-quality segmentation with just 86.9K parameters—over 95% smaller than PortraitNet. ExtremeC3Net [6] further reduced the footprint to 37.7K parameters via a dual-branch architecture, though reliance on dilated convolutions limits deployment on devices lacking efficient sparse operation support. RCRNet [7] introduced a Re-parameter Compress Residual module with multiple training branches that collapse to a single inference branch. While achieving competitive accuracy (96.33% mIoU on EG1800 with 0.77M parameters), RCRNet exhibits significant deployment limitations for embedded platforms, demonstrating the highest inference latency among lightweight portrait segmentation methods.

Efficient CNN backbones. Efficient CNN design has been crucial for enabling segmentation on constrained devices. The MobileNet series [16]–[18] evolved from depthwise separable convolutions to inverted residual blocks and later to Universal

Inverted Bottleneck modules with Mobile Multi-query Attention, yet performance often falls short on platforms with strict memory or energy constraints. Recent work has shifted toward architectures designed explicitly for TinyML. XiNet [8] discards depthwise convolutions in favor of standard convolutions with hardware-aware bottlenecks, prioritizing RAM usage and arithmetic intensity over FLOPs, with fine-grained scaling via hyperparameters controlling compute, memory, and parameter budgets. PhiNet [19] complements this with systematic optimization for RAM, compute, and Flash memory independently, enabling deployment on broader microcontroller hardware. These developments highlight the importance of co-designing segmentation algorithms with hardware-aware CNN backbones. Our approach builds upon these insights by jointly optimizing segmentation fidelity, memory footprint, and real-world latency through architectural choices and hardware-conscious design.

III. METHODOLOGY

This section presents our approach to enable portrait segmentation on embedded devices through hardware-aware architecture design. We first analyze existing lightweight methods to identify optimal baseline architectures (Section III-A), then describe our proposed SINergy architecture with its hardware-oriented design principles (Section III-B). We present microcontroller-specific adaptations for ultra-constrained environments (Section III-C), and conclude with our scalability framework that enables fine-grained adaptation across heterogeneous platforms (Section III-D).

A. Baseline Architecture Analysis

The selection of appropriate baseline architecture requires empirical evaluation beyond conventional parameter and FLOP metrics. We conduct systematic comparison of SINet [5], ExtremeC3Net [6], and RCRNet [7] to identify practical deployment characteristics on embedded platforms. On the EG1800 dataset, SINet achieves 95.29% mIoU with 86.9K parameters and 64 MMac operations, compared to ExtremeC3Net’s 94.98% mIoU with 37.7K parameters but substantially higher computational requirements of 286 MMac. Memory profiling reveals critical deployment differences: ExtremeC3Net requires 84.07 MB of RAM usage compared to SINet’s more efficient 38.78 MB, creating deployment bottlenecks on resource-constrained platforms despite its lower parameter count. RCRNet demonstrates superior accuracy (96.33% mIoU) through re-parameterization techniques but with significantly increased parameter count (772.0K) and moderate computational overhead (217 MMac). The training-time multi-branch structure provides enhanced learning capability while collapsing to efficient single-branch inference, representing a modern approach to accuracy-efficiency optimization. However, test bench results indicate that this model demonstrates the highest latency and inference consumption among the three evaluated approaches. Additionally, the absence of publicly available source code limits its applicability as a baseline

for future work. Based on operational efficiency, memory utilization, and architectural compatibility considerations, SINet provides optimal foundation for embedded optimization. However, it presents several limitations that limit efficient deployment on embedded devices. In particular:

- Skip connections across the architecture require the storage of intermediate feature maps, substantially increasing memory usage during inference.
- Parallel layer configurations of S2-modules increase memory overhead due to concurrent tensor storage,
- Depthwise convolutions used in S2-blocks exhibit poor efficiency on embedded hardware, owing to their low arithmetic intensity and high number of memory accesses [8].

B. Our Proposed SINergy

Using SINet as our baseline architecture, we propose SINergy, a hardware-aware neural network specifically designed for efficient portrait segmentation on embedded devices. The limitations identified in the baseline architecture are primarily caused by the backbone feature extractor, which accounts for the vast majority ($> 95\%$) of the computational workload in the network. To overcome these constraints, we design a new backbone based on hardware-friendly convolutional blocks that prioritize arithmetic intensity and memory efficiency over conventional mobile architectures. Our scalable backbone is specifically designed to improve computational efficiency while maintaining competitive accuracy, and enables:

- Deployment on microcontrollers, where strict memory, compute, and operator compatibility requirements prevent the use of the standard SINet backbone.
- Scalable adaptation across heterogeneous devices, enabled by hardware-aware scaling frameworks that allow fine-grained resource optimization.

SINergy presents two main architectural configurations depending on the convolutional blocks employed: SINergy- ξ , which utilizes XiConv building blocks [8], and SINergy- ϕ , which incorporates PhiNet convolutional blocks [19]. Both configurations maintain the Information Blocking Decoder mechanism present in the original SINet architecture, preserving the architectural innovations that contribute to competitive accuracy-efficiency trade-offs while systematically replacing the computationally expensive encoder. To illustrate the architecture in detail, we take the SINergy- ξ configuration as a representative example. The architecture begins with a standard Conv2d layer, followed by three sequential stages, each comprising an XiConv layer with pooling stride of 2 and a subsequent XiConv layer. The final two stages perform no spatial downsampling, consisting solely of XiConv operations without attention mechanisms. This five-stage design produces feature maps with spatial dimensions of 14×14 , requiring an upsampling layer to ensure compatibility with the Information Blocking Decoder from the original SINet architecture. Our backbone design incorporates a broadcasted skip connection originating from the initial Conv2d layer, enabling efficient

memory utilization through single tensor storage across all stages [8]. Additionally, we establish a skip connection from stage 0 of our encoder to maintain dimensional consistency with the decoder requirements. The SINergy- ϕ configuration presents an architecture analogous to that of SINergy- ξ , utilizing five PhiNet convolutional blocks with appropriately placed skip connections to maintain decoder compatibility.

C. Microcontroller Compatibility Adaptations

Microcontroller deployment requires architectural modifications to ensure compatibility with integer-only arithmetic and limited operator support. We implement three key adaptations: (1) **SINergy- ξ backbone attention removal** due to multi-dimensional softmax operations being computationally expensive and unsupported in integer-only inference engines; (2) **SINet softmax substitution** with linear normalization to avoid exponential computations; (3) **activation replacement** of SiLU with ReLU for native microcontroller support and simplified quantization. These modifications, denoted with suffix μ in model nomenclature (e.g., SINergy- ξ - μ), reduce inference latency and memory consumption while preserving functional correctness for ultra-constrained deployment scenarios.

D. Scalability Framework and Parameter Selection

The hardware-oriented backbone of SINergy comprises scalable encoder architectures that enable adaptation to diverse embedded hardware constraints through fine-grained control over computational complexity, memory footprint, and parameter count.

Both SINergy- ξ and SINergy- ϕ utilize three scaling hyperparameters. The width multiplier α controls the global scaling of convolutional filter counts, with quadratic effects on parameters, operations, and memory. The shape factor β governs filter distribution progression from the initial block (αC_{out}) to the final block ($\alpha \beta C_{out}$), enabling trade-offs between computational complexity and parameter count. The third parameter differs between configurations: SINergy- ξ employs a compression factor γ that determines the input-to-output filter ratio in compressed convolutions, while SINergy- ϕ uses an expansion factor t_0 that governs working memory requirements (RAM) through its linear relationship with dynamic tensor sizes.

Our experimental approach focuses primarily on α variation to establish the fundamental scaling characteristics of both SINergy configurations. The remaining hyperparameters (β , γ for SINergy- ξ and β , t_0 for SINergy- ϕ) remain available for fine-grained resource allocation when deploying to specific hardware platforms.

IV. EXPERIMENTS

A. Target Platforms

To evaluate the performance and scalability of our approach, we deployed the optimized architecture on five distinct platforms, representing different classes of embedded devices:

- An Nvidia Jetson AGX Xavier, a high-performance edge device typically used to run complex neural networks.

This platform is the most powerful of the four and combines an 8-core ARM v8.2 processor with a 512 CUDA-core Nvidia Volta GPU.

- Two different Raspberry Pi single board computers (i.e., RPi 4 and RPi 5), to showcase the performance of the proposed networks on easy-to-use, general-purpose hardware. While slower and less efficient than the other devices, these platforms are surprisingly capable when used for edge inference.
- An STM32H7, platform with a single ARM M7 core. This can offer high efficiency and lower power consumption at the cost of limited working memory and operator support.
- A GreenWaves GAP9, the platform with the lowest power consumption among the tested devices. It is a multi-core microcontroller based on RISC-V architecture with hardware for accelerating convolutional operations. It allows largely lower power consumption than the previous two platforms, however, with a narrower set of supported operators

B. Datasets

Our experimental evaluation employs multiple datasets to ensure comprehensive assessment and fair comparison with existing state-of-the-art methods in portrait segmentation.

EG1800. Following the methodology established in prior work [5], [6], we utilize the EG1800 dataset as our primary evaluation benchmark. The original dataset contains 1800 portrait images, primarily consisting of self-portraits captured with mobile devices. Due to invalid URL links in the original dataset, our experiments are conducted on the available subset of 1579 images, partitioned into 1309 training images and 270 validation/testing images. To enhance training diversity and ensure fair comparison with existing methods, we employ the augmented dataset used in SINet [5] and ExtremeC3Net [6], which combines the original EG1800 samples with additional synthetic data generation. The training is performed on this augmented dataset, while validation evaluation is conducted exclusively on the EG1800 validation set to maintain direct comparability with published results.

P3M-10k. We extend our evaluation to the P3M-10k dataset [20], which includes 10,421 face privacy-protected portrait images with corresponding fine matting annotations. The training partition contains 9,421 high-definition portrait images with blocked facial information. The validation set is divided into two subsets: (1) P3M-500-p provides 500 privacy-protected portraits with high-precision annotations, and (2) P3M-500-np contains 500 celebrity portrait images with disclosed facial information. For the evaluation on these datasets, we measure the segmentation accuracy (mIoU), inference latency and energy consumption. Latency measurements follow systematic protocol with 30 consecutive inferences, with the final result computed as the average of these measurements to ensure reliable performance assessment.

Fig. 2. Accuracy–latency comparison of SINergy- ξ versus SINergy- ϕ on Raspberry Pi 5. The y-axis reports EG1800 mIoU (higher is better) and the x-axis reports inference latency in ms (log-scale; lower is better); bubble size is proportional to parameter count. SINergy- ξ consistently attains higher accuracy at comparable latency.

C. Training Strategy

The training procedure follows the established two-stage methodology of SINet and ExtremeC3Net. In the first stage, the encoder is trained in isolation for 400 epochs. Subsequently, end-to-end training of the complete architecture is performed for an additional 400 epochs using the best encoder parameters as initialization. Training is conducted on a single GPU using the ADAM optimizer with an initial learning rate of 5×10^{-4} and weight decay of 2×10^{-4} . A Lovász-Hinge loss [21] is used, and batch sizes are set to 36 during encoder-only training and reduced to 24 for full network training. Input images are resized to 224×224 pixels and subjected to standard data augmentation techniques including translation, color augmentation, blur augmentation, and noise augmentation.

D. Ablation Experiments

The ablation study systematically evaluates the impact of architectural modifications on both segmentation accuracy and computational efficiency. This analysis encompasses two primary investigations: comparative evaluation between SINergy- ξ and SINergy- ϕ encoders and configuration variations within SINergy- ξ variants.

1) *Encoder Architecture Comparison:* Comparative evaluation between SINergy- ξ and SINergy- ϕ encoders reveals consistent SINergy- ξ superiority across all configurations, as shown in Figure 2. The smallest SINergy- ξ configuration ($\alpha = 0.3$) attains 91.62% mIoU, surpassing the largest SINergy- ϕ variant ($\alpha = 1.0$) at 90.32% mIoU. At equivalent latency, being based on a more recent convolutional block architecture, SINergy- ξ consistently delivers improvements exceeding 10% mIoU.

2) *SINergy- ξ Configuration Analysis:* Beyond the baseline SINergy- ξ architecture (also referred to as SINergy- ξ -Deep), we design two alternative variants to optimize the trade-off between computational efficiency and performance. These variants provide different configurations of the XiConv-based encoder to explore the impact of architectural depth and spatial resolution on segmentation accuracy. The first variant,

Fig. 3. Accuracy–latency trade-off of SINergy- ξ variants on Raspberry Pi 5. EG1800 mIoU (higher is better) is plotted against inference time in ms (lower is better); bubble size indicates parameter count. SINergy- ξ -Deep provides the best accuracy across the explored width multipliers.

SINergy- ξ -Direct, preserves the five XiConv stages while preventing downsampling upon reaching 28×28 spatial dimensions, thereby eliminating the need for the terminal upsampling layer. This adaptation requires modifying stage 2 by removing the pooling stride from the first XiConv operation, maintaining higher spatial resolution throughout the later stages of the network. The second variant, *SINergy- ξ -Compact*, removes stage 2 entirely, resulting in a four-stage architecture that includes only two blocks with pooling operations. Each of these blocks contains an XiConv layer with pooling stride 2 followed by a standard XiConv layer, while the remaining two stages consist of standard XiConv blocks. This design produces 28×28 feature maps, eliminating the upsampling requirement and representing the most parameter-efficient variant while maintaining direct compatibility with the decoder. For consistency throughout this work, when referenced without qualification, the term *SINergy- ξ* refers specifically to the baseline SINergy- ξ -Deep configuration. Figure 3 demonstrates that SINergy- ξ -Deep consistently delivers superior performance across width multiplier range $\alpha \in [0.3, 1.0]$, reaching 94.92% mIoU at $\alpha = 1.0$. SINergy- ξ -Direct exhibits improvements over SINergy- ξ -Compact while remaining systematically inferior to SINergy- ξ -Deep, demonstrating that increased spatial resolution does not yield commensurate accuracy improvements.

E. State-of-the-Art Comparison

Table I reports the performance and accuracy comparison across platforms. SINergy- ξ delivers substantial performance improvements across all platforms: SINergy- ξ ($\alpha = 0.8$) achieves approximately $2 \times$ faster inference compared to SINet while maintaining competitive 94.64% mIoU. Performance advantages become pronounced on resource-constrained platforms: on Raspberry Pi 5, SINergy- ξ achieves 5.37 ms compared to SINet’s 11.45 ms ($\sim 2.1 \times$ speedup). On the P3M-10K dataset, RCRNet demonstrates superior accuracy, particularly on privacy-protected images (95.76% compared to 95.03% for SINergy- ξ with $\alpha = 1.5$). However, SINergy- ξ variants achieve competitive performance with significantly improved efficiency characteristics, making them more suitable for resource-constrained deployment scenarios.

Fig. 4. Energy per inference across embedded platforms (lower is better), from microcontrollers (STM32H7) to a GPU edge device (Jetson Xavier). SINergy- ξ achieves consistently lower energy than lightweight baselines where comparable runs are possible; SINet and ExtremeC3Net cannot execute on STM32H7 due to memory/operator constraints.

F. Energy Efficiency Analysis

The results highlight the effectiveness of our hardware-aware design in terms of both latency and energy consumption. Compared to previous architectures, our approach allows for a $2 \times$ to $5 \times$ speedup (depending on target hardware) while maintaining the same level of accuracy. Thanks to the use of highly compatible operations, the network can be deployed even on extremely constrained embedded devices and lightweight convolutional accelerators, making near-sensor or in-sensor processing feasible in devices such as webcams or action cameras. Moreover, although the design is tailored for tinyML scenarios, we observe comparable efficiency gains on larger platforms equipped with GPUs, such as the Nvidia Jetson. Figure 4 illustrates energy per inference across platforms. Key energy efficiency characteristics:

- **STM32H7:** 241ms inference at 50mW yields 12mJ per inference, enabling battery-powered IoT applications using commercially available, general-purpose microcontrollers
- **Raspberry Pi 5:** 5.37ms at 16W yields 86mJ per inference, supporting continuous real-time processing on common embedded hardware
- **Jetson Xavier:** 4.91ms at 15W yields 74mJ per inference with GPU acceleration, showcasing the advantages of these approaches even for larger, GPU-equipped platforms
- **GAP9:** 6.4ms inference at 60mW yields 0.38mJ per inference, demonstrating the possibility of running these kinds of approaches in real time with negligible energy consumption when specialized hardware is used

G. Microcontroller Deployment Achievement

This work presents the first successful portrait segmentation deployment on microcontroller-class devices. SINergy- ξ - μ variants achieve 6-7ms latency on GAP9 and 241–692ms

TABLE I
PERFORMANCE AND ACCURACY COMPARISON ACROSS DIFFERENT DEVICES AND VALIDATION SETS

Model	Latency (ms)					Acc (%)			Latency (ms)		Acc (%)		
	Xavier CUDA	Xavier CPU	Xavier TRT	RPi 4	RPi 5	EG1800 mIoU	P3M-500p mIoU	P3M-500np mIoU	STM32 H7	GWT GAP9	EG1800 mIoU	P3M-500p mIoU	P3M-500np mIoU
PortraitFCN**	–	–	–	–	–	80.32	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
CSSNet**	–	–	–	–	–	93.37	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
SINet	7.33	20.61	7.63	47.68	11.45	94.98	95.18	95.15	×	×	×	×	×
SINet*	–	–	–	–	–	95.28	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
ExtremeC3Net	9.65	43.34	9.59	105.22	34.10	94.73	94.51	94.20	×	×	×	×	×
ExtremeC3Net*	–	–	–	–	–	94.98	–	–	–	–	–	–	–
RCRNet**	33.17	142.75	29.22	293.59	99.48	96.33	95.76	95.84	×	×	×	×	×
SINergy- ξ ($\alpha=0.8$)	4.51	8.50	4.61	23.86	5.37	94.64	94.62	94.41	241.10	6.42	93.74	93.73	93.86
SINergy- ξ ($\alpha=1.0$)	4.91	10.51	4.59	31.22	7.48	94.92	94.87	94.77	298.18	7.64	94.04	94.15	94.01
SINergy- ξ ($\alpha=1.5$)	4.37	16.22	5.15	53.52	14.00	95.24	95.30	95.21	692.45	×	94.21	94.56	94.62

* Results reported from the original papers. ** Source code not publicly available. “×” = The approach cannot run on the target platform (e.g. Out Of Memory or architecture not compatible with embedded runtimes). “–” = data not available.

on STM32H7, addressing stringent constraints typical of tiny embedded devices, including limited memory capacity, restricted operator support, and integer-only arithmetic requirements. Microcontroller compatibility is achieved with minimal accuracy degradation: across all width multipliers α , SINergy- ξ - μ remains within 1% mIoU of SINergy- ξ . For example, SINergy- ξ - μ ($\alpha = 1.0$) achieves 94.04% compared to 94.92% for SINergy- ξ , while enabling deployment on previously inaccessible hardware platforms.

V. CONCLUSIONS

This paper presents a comprehensive evaluation of hardware-aware portrait segmentation through systematic integration of efficient backbone architectures within established frameworks. Our SINergy approach demonstrates superior accuracy-efficiency trade-offs compared to existing lightweight methods, enabling practical deployment across heterogeneous embedded platforms from microcontrollers to edge computing devices. Our hardware-aware design achieves significant performance improvements, delivering 2× to 5× speedup compared to existing approaches while maintaining competitive accuracy across all evaluated platforms. Most notably, we demonstrate the first successful portrait segmentation deployment on microcontroller-class devices, achieving 94.04% mIoU with 241ms inference time on consumer MCUs and under 7ms on specialized accelerators. The approach also exhibits superior energy efficiency through hardware-aware design principles, making battery-powered IoT applications feasible. Additionally, SINergy provides cross-platform scalability with fine-grained control over accuracy-efficiency trade-offs, enabling adaptation to diverse hardware constraints. Experimental results demonstrate that integrating hardware-aware scaling principles for portrait segmentation yields clear advantages over conventional lightweight architectures. The proposed SINergy design offers superior deployment characteristics in resource-constrained environments, delivering substantially improved performance–power trade-offs compared to prior approaches.

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